

MINIMIZATION OF THE OUT-OF-PLANE THERMAL DEFORMATION OF CFRP REFLECTORS BY STACKING SEQUENCE OPTIMIZATION

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated methods to mitigate the out-of-plane thermal deformation of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) reflectors due to fiber orientation error. CFRP exhibits high specific elasticity and low coefficient of thermal expansion. Therefore, it is regarded as a suitable material for reflectors of high-precision space observatories. However, it had been made clear that non-negligible out-of-plane thermal deformation occurs on CFRP reflectors due to the existence of fiber orientation errors of each layer. In this study, as a first step to find the method to suppress the out-of-plane thermal deformation of CFRP reflectors due to fiber orientation errors, the out-of-plane thermal deformation of CFRP laminated plates with some different patterns of stacking sequences was analyzed. The result indicated that increasing the number of layers by using as thin prepreg as possible is an effective method. Also, it was made clear that altering the stacking sequence while maintaining the number of layers is effective, which implies the possibility of further suppression of the thermal deformation by stacking sequence optimization. Then, the stacking sequence of a CFRP laminate was optimized by means of Genetic Algorithm. As a result, it was demonstrated that the out-of-plane thermal deformation can be suppressed by stacking sequence optimization.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to recent advances in space astronomy, high-precision space telescopes are highly demanded. High-precision and large reflectors (mirrors) are essential to realize those telescopes. Because of severe requirements for launching space telescopes, it is important to reduce the weight of the reflectors. Moreover, they must have high shape stability against severe temperature variations in space. Thus, the material of space-based, high-precision reflectors must have high specific elasticity and low coefficient of thermal expansion.

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) exhibits specifications mentioned above and is regarded as

a next-generation material of the space-based, high-precision reflectors. Abusafieh et al. studied the effects of moisture absorption and microcracks in CFRP on the dimensional stability of CFRP reflectors and concluded that CFRP can be used for high-precision structures that require micrometer-orders of dimensional accuracy [1]. The long-term deformation of CFRP, including creep deformation, moisture absorption, self-shrinking, and residual stress relaxation, were investigated by Arao et al. [2, 3] Yoon et al. examined the effect of thermal deformation and outgassing deformation of the composite structure of a telescope on its optical performance, and concluded that the effect of thermal deformation was much higher than that of outgassing deformation [4].

As previously mentioned, space telescopes are exposed to severe temperature variations in space. Accordingly, to discuss the feasibility of space-based CFRP reflectors, the thermal deformation of CFRP needs to be investigated. In a previous study, the authors fabricated a reflector model composed of CFRP laminate and measured its thermal deformation [5]. As a result, it was made clear that unexpected and non-negligible out-of-plane thermal deformation would occur on CFRP reflectors. Furthermore, they investigated the cause of this thermal deformation and pointed out that the effect of errors of fiber orientation angle have significant effect [6]. Fiber orientation errors are inevitable in manufacturing CFRP laminates. Therefore, the out-of-plane thermal deformation due to the existence of fiber orientation errors must be suppressed.

In this study, as a first step, the out-of-plane thermal deformation of CFRP laminated plates due to fiber orientation errors was investigated and the method to mitigate the effect of the fiber orientation error was considered. First, the effect of increasing the number of layers and altering the stacking sequence of quasi-isotropic laminates was investigated. Then, the stacking sequence was optimized using genetic algorithms to minimize the effect of the fiber orientation errors, not limited to quasi-isotropic laminates.

2 EVALUATION OF THE THERMAL DEFORMATION

In this study, the curvature of CFRP plates with different stacking sequences generated by thermal deformation due to the existence of fiber orientation errors was calculated analytically using the classical lamination theory. The flow of the analysis and evaluation is described below.

Here, a CFRP plate composed of n layers is assumed. Its stacking sequence without fiber orientation error is assumed to be symmetric. First, the curvature of the plate generated by thermal deformation due to the existence of a fiber orientation error in a single layer is considered. The curvature of the plate in the direction of θ to the 0-degree-direction of laminate with the fiber orientation error of e exists in a single layer, $\kappa^T(e, \theta)$, can be calculated as follows [7]:

$$\kappa^T(e, \theta) = \kappa_{xx}^T(e) \cos^2 \theta + \kappa_{yy}^T(e) \sin^2 \theta + \frac{1}{2} \kappa_{xy}^T(e) \sin 2\theta. \quad (1)$$

where $\kappa_{xx}^T(e)$, $\kappa_{yy}^T(e)$, and $\kappa_{xy}^T(e)$ (denoted by $\kappa_{ij}^T(e)$ below) are the components of curvature calculated by the classical lamination theory. By Taylor-expanding these components,

$$\kappa_{ij}^T(e) \approx \kappa_{ij}^T(0) + \left(\frac{d\kappa_{ij}^T}{de} \right)_{e=0} e. \quad (2)$$

When $e = 0$, which means there is no fiber orientation error, no curvature is generated. Therefore,

$$\kappa_{ij}^T(0) = 0. \quad (3)$$

Thus, these components can be described as follows:

$$\kappa_{ij}^T(e) = c_{ij}e, \quad (4)$$

where c_{ij} is constant and equal to values of $d\kappa_{ij}^T/de$ at $e = 0$. By substituting equation (4) into (1),

$$\kappa^T(e, \theta) = e \left(c_{xx} \cos^2 \theta + c_{yy} \sin^2 \theta + \frac{1}{2} c_{xy} \sin 2\theta \right). \quad (5)$$

When fiber orientation errors exist in every layer independently, the curvature will be the sum of curvatures calculated assuming fiber orientation errors in each layer individually.

The magnitude of the out-of-plane thermal deformation is evaluated by a limit value of the standard deviation of the curvature in all directions, σ . When fiber orientation errors exist in every layer independently, this value can be calculated by the same value considering the fiber orientation error in single layer as follows: [8]

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\sum_m \sigma_m^2}, \quad (6)$$

where σ_m is the limit value of the standard deviation of the curvature when a fiber orientation error exists in m -th layer only. Assuming that the fiber orientation error follows a normal distribution, σ_m can be calculated as follows:

$$\sigma_m = \sqrt{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_0^{\pi} \kappa^T(e, \theta)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{\pi} \cdot f(e) d\theta de}. \quad (7)$$

where $1/\pi$ and $f(e)$ are probability density functions of θ in an interval $[0, \pi)$, and e in an interval $(-\infty, \infty)$, respectively. By substituting equation (5), the integration in the radical sign is divided into two terms,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^2 f(e) de \int_0^{\pi} \frac{1}{\pi} \left(c_{xx} \cos^2 \theta + c_{yy} \sin^2 \theta + \frac{1}{2} c_{xy} \sin 2\theta \right)^2 d\theta. \quad (8)$$

The former term is a definition of the variation of e . Here, the standard deviation of the distribution of fiber orientation error is assumed to be s , then the value of the former term is equal to s^2 . The latter term can be calculated as follows:

$$\frac{1}{4} (c_{xx} + c_{yy})^2 + \frac{1}{8} \left[(c_{xx} - c_{yy})^2 + c_{xy}^2 \right]. \quad (9)$$

Thus, σ_m can be calculated as follows:

$$\sigma_m = s \sqrt{\frac{1}{4} (c_{xx} + c_{yy})^2 + \frac{1}{8} \left[(c_{xx} - c_{yy})^2 + c_{xy}^2 \right]}. \quad (10)$$

By substituting values of σ_m calculated by equation (10) into (6), the extent of the out-of-plane thermal deformation of the CFRP laminate due to the existence of fiber orientation errors of s in the standard deviation is obtained.

3 RELATION BETWEEN THE STACKING SEQUENCE AND OUT-OF-PLANE THERMAL DEFORMATION

As a first step to find methods to mitigate the effect of fiber orientation errors on the out-of-plane thermal deformation of CFRP plates, the magnitude of the out-of-plane thermal deformation of quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates with 8 or 16 layers was calculated to assess the effect of changing the number of layers and stacking sequence. The total thickness of the laminates was 0.8 mm. Thus, the thickness of each layer was 0.1 mm for 8-layer, and 0.05 mm for 16-layer. The stacking sequence for 8-layer was $[0/-45/90/45]_s$, which is the same with that of the reflector model used in the previous studies [5, 6]. On the other hand, there were two different stacking sequences for 16-layers. One was $[0_2/-45_2/90_2/45_2]_s$, and another was $[0/-45/90/45]_{2s}$. Assumed material constants are listed in Table 1. These values were measured by a tensile test and a thermo-mechanical analysis on the same material of that of the reflector model used in previous studies. In this analysis, the standard deviation of fiber orientation error was assumed to be 0.4° , according to the previous study by Arao et al. [9]

Calculated results are summarized in Table 2. By comparing $[0/-45/90/45]_s$ with $[0_2/-45_2/90_2/45_2]_s$, it can be understood that the magnitude of thermal deformation can be mitigated by increasing the number of layers. That means that using as thin prepreg as possible to fabricate CFRP reflectors is

Table 1: Material constants assumed in the analysis.

E_{LL}	340 GPa
E_{TT}	5.2 GPa
G_{LT}	3.9 GPa
ν_{LT}	0.35
α_L	$-0.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$
α_T	$35 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$

Table 2: The magnitude of out-of-plane thermal deformation due to fiber orientation errors of quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates with some different numbers of layers and different stacking sequences.

Number of layer	Stacking sequence	Standard deviation [$\times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}/\text{K}$]
8	$[0/-45/90/45]_s$	69.93
16	$[0_2/-45_2/90_2/45_2]_s$	49.77
16	$[0/-45/90/45]_{2s}$	25.73

effective. On the other hand, comparing $[0_2/-45_2/90_2/45_2]_s$ with $[0/-45/90/45]_{2s}$, it can be understood that the magnitude of thermal deformation can also be mitigated by altering the stacking sequence with the same number of layers. This result implied the possibility of further suppression of the out-of-plane thermal deformation by stacking sequence optimization.

4 STACKING SEQUENCE OPTIMIZATION

4.1 Optimization parameters

The stacking sequence of a CFRP laminate was optimized in order to minimize the magnitude of out-of-plane thermal deformation due to fiber orientation errors. In this optimization, genetic algorithm (GA) was adopted. Following constraints were imposed:

- Thickness of the laminate: 0.8 mm,
- Number of layers: 8 or 16,
- Fiber orientation on the uppermost and lowermost layers: 0° ,
- Stacking sequence: Symmetric.

Therefore, the numbers of design variables for 8- and 16-layers were three and seven, respectively. Thus the stacking sequences for 8- and 16-layers were $[0/\theta_1/\theta_2/\theta_3]_s$ and $[0/\theta_1/\theta_2/\theta_3/\theta_4/\theta_5/\theta_6/\theta_7]_s$, respectively, where θ_i is optimized fiber orientation angle in $(i + 1)$ -th layer. The fiber orientation of the second layer, θ_1 , had the range between -90° to 0° , and those of other layers had the range between -90° and 90° . Each of these design values was encoded as a 9-bit binary and the fitness value,

$$\frac{\sigma_{OI}}{\sigma}, \quad (11)$$

where σ_{OI} and σ are the magnitude of the out-of-plane thermal deformation with quasi-isotropic stacking sequences ($[0/-45/90/45]_s$ for 8-layer, and $[0/-45/90/45]_{2s}$ for 16-layers) and that with an arbitrary stacking sequence, respectively, was maximized (i.e. σ was minimized) through operations of GA which consists of natural selection, crossover, and mutation. The GA parameters used for the optimization are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: GA parameters used in the optimization.

Number of generation	500
Population of each generation	100
Number of bit	9
Crossover probability	0.5
Mutation probability	0.02
Generation gap	0.5

4.2 Optimization results

Figure 1 shows the history of the highest fitness value for each generation for 8- and 16-layers. As shown in this figure, the fitness value converged in 500 generations.

The optimized stacking sequences and the magnitude of out-of-plane thermal deformation due to fiber orientation errors of 0.4° in standard deviation are listed in Table 4. The magnitudes of thermal deformation for 8- and 16-layers decreased approximately 30% and 16%, respectively, compared to the quasi-isotropic stacking sequences. Thus, it was demonstrated that stacking sequence optimization is an effective method to mitigate the effect of fiber orientation errors on the out-of-plane thermal deformation of CFRP laminates.

Figure 1: The history of the highest fitness value for each generation.

Table 4: The magnitude of out-of-plane thermal deformation due to fiber orientation errors of a CFRP laminated plate with the optimum stacking sequences.

Stacking sequence	Standard deviation [$\times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}/\text{K}$]
$[0/-47.1/71.4/4.2]_s$	48.63
$[0/-56.3/66.8/50.6/-72.1/48.9/-37.3/-6.0]_s$	21.61

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, as a first step to find the method to suppress the out-of-plane thermal deformation of CFRP reflectors due to fiber orientation errors, the curvature of quasi-isotropic CFRP plates with some different stacking sequences generated by thermal deformation was analyzed. The result indicated that

increasing the number of layers and altering the order of layers of quasi-isotropic stacking sequences were effective, which implies the possibility of further suppression of the thermal deformation by stacking sequence optimization. Then, the stacking sequence was optimized by means of Genetic Algorithm to minimize the out-of-plane thermal deformation. As a result, it was demonstrated that the out-of-plane thermal deformation of CFRP plates can be mitigated by optimizing the stacking sequences. As a future work, the effect of stacking sequence optimization should be experimentally investigated.

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